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Anton Chubenko

Doctor of Law, Professor,
Director of the Academy of Financial Monitoring,
Kyiv, Ukraine
chubenko@i.ua

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THE EXPERIENCE OF THE UNITED KINGDOM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL AML AND ANTI-CORRUPTION SYSTEMS IN UKRAINE: COMPARATIVE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Abstract. The UK is one of the world's most open countries. Its economic level is built on extensive and productive relationships across the globe. However, the UK open status as of a global finance center leads to the risk of illicit financial flows.

Combating money laundering and corruption prevention – general globe tendency. The USA has also got the documents of strategical importance to provide the tax policy.

Financial authorities of Ukraine, the UK, and the USA are the participants of the system to counteract to money laundering and financing terrorism both at national and international levels.

The purpose of the article is to study the UK experience to develop Ukrainian AML and anticorruption system.

In 2015–2016, the UK and Ukraine published first ever national risk assessment of money laundering and terrorist financing, setting out candidly the areas where action was needed.

Our legislation is constantly supplemented with the provisions on combating money laundering, which are in line with international standards. Changes in the suspicious transaction reporting and supervisory regime are conducted both in the UK and in Ukraine.

The UK aggressively pursues money laundering and terrorist financing investigations and prosecutions, achieving 1400 convictions each year for money laundering. UK law enforcement authorities have powerful tools to obtain beneficial ownership and other information, including through effective public-private partnerships, and make good use of this information in their investigations.

Some key authorities were established in Ukraine, including the National Agency of Ukraine for finding, tracing and management of assets derived from corruption and other crimes. The functions of the Agency (the ARMA) are understandable for most countries of the world, but absolutely new in the system of state authorities of Ukraine. The UK has got special legislation, the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002 (POCA).

Ukraine has been proactive in seeking international co-operation through outgoing MLA requests with regards to investigations of domestic ML or other major predicate crimes.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the current lack of court decisions on the confiscation of seized assets is connected with the ongoing pre-trial investigations into relevant criminal proceedings, since the investigated crimes are complex, requiring a large amount of investigative and other procedural actions.

Consequently, an important aspect of the Ukrainian system's operation is the exchange of information. The UK provides unique opportunities for international co-operation on cases and enhancing international public/private information sharing. The UK courts can also issue an order to freeze or confiscate this property.

The UK has significantly strengthened its AML/CFT framework since its last evaluation particularly in relation to operational co-ordination among law enforcement agencies, stronger investigative tools, mechanisms to facilitate public/private information sharing.

This is especially important on the basis that Ukraine should show progress in the formation of a new national legislator AML/CFT, in particular when adopting the basic Law to implement EU Directive 2015/849 2015.

Keywords: corruptio prevention; combating money laundering; the National Agency of Ukraine for finding, tracing and management of assets derived from corruption and other crimes.

The UK is one of the world's largest and most open economies, whose strength is built on extensive and productive relationships across the globe. Government responsibility for national security and financial services, we want the UK to continue to be an attractive country for legitimate business and a leading global financial centre. But we also recognize that the UK's openness and status as a global financial centre exposes it to the risk of illicit financial flows.

Money laundering and terrorist financing are significant threats. Recent terrorist attacks in London, Manchester and elsewhere highlight the importance of the fight to deprive terrorists of the resources they need. Serious and organized crime has been estimated to cost the UK tens of billions of pounds every year. That is why we must continue to crack down on dirty money, strengthening the UK's security and prosperity as well as that of our partners overseas.

The UK is not alone in facing these threats, and we work hand in hand with our international partners to tackle them. The UK has been at the forefront of recent global efforts to shut down safe spaces for money laundering and terrorist financing. The 2016 London Anti-Corruption Summit led to over 600 specific commitments made by more than 40 countries and six major international organizations¹.

¹ Cooperation in the sphere of financial monitoring and anti-corruption efforts: international and national aspects: joint international scientific and practical workshop (Odesa 2016) 148.

These issues are relevant throughout the world. Such strategic relevant documents for the implementation of tax policies are also exist in the United States of America.

The experience of the USA, in particular on the functioning of the departments of Criminal Investigation (CI) Internal Revenue Service (IRS), which operate not only in the USA but also abroad. The main objective of these units is to combat tax crimes worldwide.

Internal Revenue Service (IRS) of the USA applies long-term activities. So such IRS Strategic Plan of the Fiscal Service on 2014–2017 (Strategic Plan, Fiscal Years 2014–2017) exists and determines how the Internal Revenue Service (IRS) of the USA will improve taxpayer service and provide legislation for several years. Implementation of the Plan is monitored to evaluate progress in achieving the objectives specified in the Strategic Plan².

Fiscal authorities of Ukraine, Great Britain and the USA are the participants of the AML/CFT system, either national or international levels. Thus, if in the mentioned article “Cooperation in the sphere of financial monitoring and anti-corruption efforts: international and national aspects” we have considered the IRS role, then in the latest one called “Anti-corruption and anti-legalization role of the General Prosecutor of Ukraine through the prism of international standards”³, we did an analysis of the work of the prosecutors in the AML process.

This article will be devoted to a comparative method of research of the UK experience in AML issues. We are grateful to those scientists who conduct research in these areas, in particular of the following: N. Akhtyrskaya, S. Bychkova, M. Loshitskyi, S. Minchenko, D. Pavlov, V. Filatova, T. Fulei, H. Khembach, O. Yanovska and other scientists.

The purpose of the article is to study the UK experience to develop Ukrainian AML and anti-corruption system.

In 2015–2016, the UK and Ukraine published its first ever national risk assessment of money laundering and terrorist financing, setting out candidly the areas where action was needed. In 2016, the government published an action plan outlining the most significant reforms to our anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing regime in over a decade.

Ukraine has also prepared a number of strategic documents based on the NRA results and a corresponding plan has been prepared. This work was intensified in 2014, when the NRA was launched⁴.

² A Chubenko, ‘National Tax security and prospects of usage of experience of the Internal Revenue Service (IRS) of the United States to combat shadow economy in Ukraine’ (2017) 1(25) Public Law 18–25.

³ A Chubenko, ‘Anti-corruption and anti-legalization role of the General Prosecutor of Ukraine through the prism of international standards’ (2018) 5 (1) European Science 200.

⁴ Implementation of the national risk assessment of money laundering and terrorist financing as an element of the state policy of shadowing of the Ukrainian economy: joint international seminar of the OSCE and the State Financial Monitoring Service of Ukraine (Kyiv 2014) 100.

UK government many of the actions in this plan have now been launched or delivered. The Criminal Finances Act 2017 provided tough new powers such as Unexplained Wealth Orders for tackling money laundering and terrorist financing. The Money Laundering Regulations 2017 bring the latest international regulatory standards into UK law. Reforms of the suspicious activity reports regime and the supervisory regime are underway, and our commitment to public-private partnership is embodied in the development of the Joint Money Laundering Intelligence Taskforce, which continues to deliver concrete outcomes in disrupting criminal activity.

Ukraine is also working on the implementation of similar provisions, which was positively noted in international acts.

This year, the UK's anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing regime will be assessed by the Financial Action Task Force. The UK will be evaluated for the first time against the strengthened global standards introduced in 2012.

This government is determined to demonstrate the UK's commitment to tackling illicit financial flows. We must not stand still. As money laundering and terrorist financing risks continue to evolve, so must our understanding and our response. This second national risk assessment shows how that has happened since 2015.

This assessment will provide a critical component of the evidence base for the response to money laundering and terrorist financing over the coming years. The government is confident that by responding to these risks, and through continued partnership between government, law enforcement, supervisors and the private sector, we can ensure that the UK economy is a hostile environment for illicit finance and an open, attractive destination for legitimate business.

The UK encounters different terrorism and TF risks in mainland UK from those faced in Northern Ireland. Authorities in all jurisdictions demonstrate a good understanding of their particular TF risks and the nature, scale, and number of TF cases pursued across the UK is in line with its distinct risk profile. The assessment team based these conclusions on numerous case studies demonstrating the types of cases pursued; statistics; a review of the NRA and other relevant assessments; and discussions with the National Terrorist Finance Investigation Unit (NTFIU), the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS), the Police Service of Northern Ireland (PSNI), the Public Prosecution Service of Northern Ireland (PPSNI), and other LEAs.

While international terrorism is assessed to be a severe threat to the UK, the majority of terrorist attack plots have been low complexity, planned and executed by lone actor extremists. The 2017 NRA therefore recognizes the UK's TF threat as predominantly UK-based, with the highest risks posed by: low-level, self-funded attackers; individuals providing small amounts of funding to FTFs; or individuals financing their own travel plans. As a result, MSBs, cash couriers and retail banking were considered at high risk of abuse for TF. TF risks in the NPO sector overall were considered to be low with certain parts of the sector facing significantly higher

risks. The LEAs also noted a propensity for individuals to abuse benefits or commit low level fraud to generate funds for terrorist activity. This understanding of risk was consistently shared by all relevant LEAs and prosecutorial agencies. Numerous case studies illustrate the UK's proactive investigation, prosecution and conviction of a range of TF activity, consistent with its identified risks⁵.

The UK aggressively pursues money laundering and terrorist financing investigations and prosecutions, achieving 1400 convictions each year for money laundering. UK law enforcement authorities have powerful tools to obtain beneficial ownership and other information, including through effective public-private partnerships, and make good use of this information in their investigations. However, the UK financial intelligence unit needs a substantial increase in its resources and the suspicious activity reporting regime needs to be modernized and reformed.

An Act to establish the Assets Recovery Agency and make provision about the appointment of its Director and his functions (including Revenue functions), to provide for confiscation orders in relation to persons who benefit from criminal conduct and for restraint orders to prohibit dealing with property, to allow the recovery of property which is or represents property obtained through unlawful conduct or which is intended to be used in unlawful conduct, to make provision about money laundering, to make provision about investigations relating to benefit from criminal conduct or to property which is or represents property obtained through unlawful conduct or to money laundering, to make provision to give effect to overseas requests and orders made where property is found or believed to be obtained through criminal conduct, and for connected purposes.

As we have already mentioned in the article "National Agency of Ukraine for finding, tracing and management of assets derived from corruption and other crimes: formation of a new central executive body"⁶, Asset Recovery and Management Agency (ARMA) is one of the powerful central executive bodies with a special anti-corruption status. However, for the successful implementation of the functions assigned to it, it is necessary to implement certain organizational and jurisdictional actions, primarily at the government level.

The functions of the National Agency of Ukraine for Finding, Tracing and Management of Assets Derived from Corruption and Other Crimes (hereinafter – the ARMA) are understandable for most countries of the world, but absolutely new in the system of state authorities of Ukraine. Today, for most countries of the European Union, the existence of agencies like the ARMA is a long-established

⁵ The National Risk Assessment of Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing 2017 <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/655198/National_risk_assessment_of_money_laundering_and_terrorist_financing_2017_pdf_web.pdf> accessed 30 December 2018.

⁶ A Chubenko, 'National Agency of Ukraine for finding, tracing and management of assets derived from corruption and other crimes: formation of a new central executive body' *The shadow economy: world trends and Ukrainian realities: interdepartmental scientific-practical conference* (Kyiv 2017).

practice. In particular, Article 10 of the EU Directive of 04/03/2014 No 2014/42 / EU requires all EU Member States to take measures on effective asset management, which have been seized, as well as establishment of special institutions responsible for managing such assets in order to preserve them or preserve their economic value.

Thus, management of the seized property is one of the functions of the ARMA and it is the implementation of relevant EU practices on the management of a seized property. This function is not just another regulatory activity of the state, it creates a fundamentally new mechanism for public-private partnerships, the analogies of which did not exist in Ukraine, and involves the development of new markets of management of seized property and the market of seized property (but not yet confiscated).

In UK, the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002 (POCA) sets out the law in relation to the recovery of criminal assets with criminal being the most commonly used power. Confiscation normally only occurs after a conviction has taken place. The 2002 Act codified previous legislation and provided that of can be recovered where there has been no conviction i.e. cash seizure, civil recovery etc.

Simply put, the primary aim of POCA 2002 is to close loop-holes and deprive criminals of the use of their assets, recover the proceeds of crime and to show that crime doesn't pay. It also has the effect of causing business people to think twice before undertaking a criminal enterprise and for those who advise such people to give robust advice so that such criminal enterprises don't get started.

Between 2010 and 2014 the Home Office has indicated that more than £746 million of criminal assets has been seized. Over the same period, assets worth more than £2,5 billion have been frozen denying criminals access to these resources and £93 million has been returned to victims. As of December 2014, there were nearly 1,250 live confiscation orders under the responsibility of the Crown Prosecution Service, amounting to nearly £500 million, of which 31,5% was deemed collectable.

In addition, the 2002 Act confers a number of investigative powers and tools: search and seizure; production orders and disclosure orders; orders for of assets to prevent assets being disposed of to a confiscation order being imposed.

The Act is comprehensive and sets out the legislative schemes of recovery which is broken down into parts. The relevant parts for POCA cases which arise in England are: Confiscation in England and Wales, Civil Recovery, including cash seizure, Revenue Functions, Money Laundering, and Investigation⁷.

We will not dwell on the specifics of building special AML/CFT laws, given that a new version of the Law has been prepared based on EU directive 2015/849 2015.

⁷ Proceeds of Crime Act [2002] Chapter 29 <<http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/29>> accessed 30 December 2018.

But it is worth noting that we prepared comments on this law⁸ earlier and it is available in free access to all who are interested or engaged in this process.

We should note that the main areas of ARMA activities are asset finding and tracing. ARMA is responsible for finding (activity aimed at establishing the fact of existence) and tracing (activity aimed at determination the location) of assets – property that are subject to seizure in criminal proceedings.

ARMA is entitled to support criminal investigation cases by means of:

- taking measures on tracing and finding of assets upon requests of the investigators, detectives, pre-trial investigation authorities, prosecutor's office and courts and cooperate with such authorities for the purpose of seizure and confiscation of such assets;

- ensuring pre-MLA international cooperation with relevant authorities of foreign states, international organizations dealing in this sphere by taking measures on tracing and finding of assets as well as requesting them on asset finding and tracing activities;

- filing claims with a court to find invalid regulatory legal acts and individual decisions, contracts issued/made in violation of the requirements and limitations set forth in legislation;

- taking part in representation of the State of Ukraine in foreign jurisdictional bodies in cases related to return of assets derived from corruption and other crimes.

Asset Management area. Executing court decisions, ARMA is entitled for management of assets seized or confiscated in criminal proceedings in order to preserve or maintain economic value of the assets by:

- transferring into management using asset management agreement;

- disposal – sale with further cash disposal in state banking system temporary – till the end of the criminal proceedings.

State policy development area. ARMA is authorized to formulate and implement state policy in the sphere of tracing, finding and management of assets by:

- drafting proposals for formulation and implementation of the state policy (draft laws, bylaws, binding regulatory legal acts of the ARMA);

- concluding multi-agency international agreements on cooperation with authorities of foreign states the competence of which includes the issues concerning finding, tracing and management of assets derived from corruption and other crimes;

- providing clarifications, methodological and advisory assistance to investigators, detectives, prosecutors and judges with regard to the issues of finding, tracing, evaluation and management of assets;

⁸ A Chubenko, M Loshytskyi and others, *On Prevention and Counteraction to Legalization (Laundering) of the Criminal Proceeds, Terrorism Financing and Financing of Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction: scientific and practical comment to the law of Ukraine* (Vaite 2015) 816.

– developing and keeping of the Unified State Register of Assets Seized in Criminal Proceedings, which shall contain, for instance, information on assets, which have been seized in criminal proceedings, court decision on seizure and/or cancellation of seizure, number of criminal proceedings in the Unified Register of Pre-Trial Investigations and other relevant information.

Confiscation is also facilitated under POCA through automatic assumptions being made in certain cases where the offender has been found to have a criminal lifestyle. The assumptions apply to many of the UK's priority offences including ML, drug trafficking, people trafficking, and terrorism. In these cases, the court will assume that any property transferred to the defendant or expenditure by the defendant in the six years preceding criminal proceedings, or any property held by the defendant after the date of conviction, is assumed to have been obtained through criminality. The value of this property is then used in calculating the benefit obtained by the defendant for the purpose of confiscation (unless the defendant can prove otherwise or there would be a serious risk of injustice if the assumption were to be made).

All LEAs, including regional police forces, have specialized proceeds of crime units which provide in-house expertise (these include: the NCA Proceeds of Crime Centre; the SFO Proceeds of Crime and International Assistance Division; the HMRC Fraud Investigation Service Proceeds of Crime Team; the HMRC Proceeds of Crime Intervention Team; the FCA Criminal Prosecutions Team asset recovery sub-team; the PSNI Economic Crime Unit; and the Regional Asset Recovery Teams of the England and Wales police forces). These units include POCA accredited financial investigators who receive accreditation and training from the NCA Proceeds of Crime Centre and are able to exercise POCA powers, including search, seizure, and application for restraint. Financial investigators in Police Scotland also receive accredited training. The specialist teams have proved effective. The HMRC Proceeds of Crime Intervention Team (dedicated to cash intervention) has seized GBP 13,5 million and forfeited GBP 7,5 million since it was established in April 2015, while the FCA Criminal Prosecutions Team's asset recovery sub-team had secured approximately GBP 11 million as at March 2018.

In deciding whether to pursue asset recovery, the UK is primarily focused on output, but also takes into account the type or nature of offending involved. The NCA Confiscation Framework guides investigators on the priorities, factors and considerations in deciding to pursue confiscation. While it is not focused on specific crime types, its focus on delivering outcomes and outputs against high priority threats does encourage the pursuit of confiscation in cases involving high-end ML, organized immigration crime, and modern slavery and human trafficking. In pursuing the enforcement of confiscation orders, the CPS, the NCA, and HMRC identify priority cases based on the value of the outstanding debt as well as whether the offending involved serious and organized crime.

Large, multinational financial institutions have made significant improvements in their risk management of correspondent banking relationships following a decade of high profile enforcement actions by foreign regulators and remedial efforts required by the FCA in conjunction with foreign regulators. This remains a work in progress at some large institutions, but the FCA demonstrated a strong commitment to working with UK-based institutions to ensure that effective controls are in place.

Large firms with substantial correspondent banking books also have groupwide policies and procedures related to AML/CFT and targeted financial sanctions compliance, and have substantially expanded their compliance staff over the last decade. While significant progress has been made, some gaps in compliance related to correspondent banking persist, particularly at smaller banks. This was demonstrated in a 2014 survey by the FCA which found that while some retail, wholesale, and private banks had implemented effective AML/CFT and sanctions controls, significant and widespread weaknesses persisted at some firms (including in relation to correspondent banking, EDD and the ongoing monitoring of high risk clients). Particularly serious issues were found at six banks, four of which voluntarily limited their business activities until weaknesses are corrected, three were required to appoint a skilled person to conduct a more detailed review and make recommendations for improvements, and three conducted remedial work under the guidance of external consultants. The FCA took enforcement action against two of these banks, as well as updating regulatory guidance with further examples of good practice. The FCA has seen significant improvements as a result.

Remedial efforts by the FCA, reputational concerns, and enforcement efforts by the UK, high-profile actions taken by foreign regulators, and the establishment Senior Managers and Certification Regime (SMCR) and its attendant liabilities on senior management have led to continued progress in addressing these issues. The gap between examinations of SAMLP and PAMLP banks and limited number of smaller bank examinations, however, leads to an uneven playing field in terms of correspondent banking policies and procedures.

Banks and MSBs interviewed by the assessment team all stated that they analyze new products and services for ML/TF risks prior to their introduction to the market. The assessment team was satisfied with the examples of policies and procedures provided by these firms. However, discussions with the private sector raised concerns that some of the EABs firms providing online services, with no faceto-face contact with their clients, may not adequately fulfill their AML/CFT obligations.

In the UK context, banking institutions and MSBs conduct wire transfers. In June 2017, the UK adopted new EU requirements on cross-border wire transfer reporting which contain new obligations for the FIs that are subject to them. The FCA monitors banks' compliance with new legislative requirements as part of its

ongoing supervisory engagement. It has not identified any significant issues with firms' implementation of the new wire transfer regulations. The FSA (predecessor to the FCA) conducted a review of firms' compliance with previous wire transfer legislation in 2011 and found no major weaknesses.

HMRC noted that MSBs, in most cases, apply the appropriate identity checks and record-keeping where the requirements to establish the identity of the payer (originator) are triggered. HMRC also noted that compliance is also reinforced because the MLRs overlap with the EU's fund transfer regulations requiring payment institutions to collect and retain information on payers and payees when transferring funds (in addition to the CDD requirements in the MLRs).

All interviewed firms stated that they ran names through sanctions checks prior to customer on-boarding. Large financial institutions and professional gatekeepers demonstrated more sophisticated understanding of sanctions risks related to Iran and DPRK and have more complex risk management and policies and procedures in place to manage these risks. Some small and medium-sized FIs and financial gatekeepers have a less than uniform understanding of sanctions-related risks and have less sophisticated sanctions compliance programs, as demonstrated by the FCA's 2014 survey. Firms have, however, improved their sanctions compliance programs over the last decade in response to FCA activity and the activities and awareness raising from OFSI.

Industry representatives and authorities focused on sanctions agree that due to the vast breadth of the legal, accounting, TCSPs, HVDs, and EABs, these industries have inconsistent levels of understanding of their sanctions obligations. The Gambling Commission provides guidance in relation to these obligations and the National Casino Forum provides guidelines on how casinos can meet their sanctions obligations, including making use of database suppliers for sanctioned persons checks.

Overall, firms met with during the evaluation understand and implement their reporting obligations adequately; however, it is not clear this applies equally across all sectors as SAR filing is low in some sectors. SAR filings across some of the biggest sectors in the UK show a healthy trend, and it appears that the amount of defensive filing has declined. The UK receives more than 450 000 SARs a year which provides a rich source of financial intelligence for LEAs. While concerns remain about the quality of reports filed, work is ongoing between relevant authorities and firms to improve quality and remind firms of their obligations.

In Ukraine, banks are also members of the AML system and submit a certain number of SARs. The National Bank of Ukraine is the entity of state financial monitoring which exercises state regulation and supervision in the sphere of prevention and counteraction to legalization (laundering) of the proceeds from crime or financing terrorism with regard to banks, payment institutions and members of payment systems being banking institutions.

The powers of the National Bank regarding measures of impact were reported by us at an interdepartmental scientific and practical workshop on “Topical issues of using the possibilities of unscheduled documentary audits and other inspections in criminal proceedings” and our report was called “Authorities of the national bank of Ukraine on the imposition of administrative fines”⁹.

SARs filing is highly concentrated on a few institutions. Banks contribute almost 85% of the total SAR filings, with four banks contributing 80% of the reporting. Although this is consistent with the consolidated nature of the UK’s banking sector (five banks account for over 85% of the total market share and banks are constantly involved in the movement of money and therefore most likely to spot a suspicious transactions), it does not explain the low level of reporting across other sectors.

While large banks met with at the onsite have a window of 30/60 days to undertake their own investigation prior to filing SARs, there is a requirement to report matters requiring immediate attention to the UKFIU and all confirmed that they report SARs as soon as they reach the threshold of suspicion. The UKFIU accepts bulk reporting by the main reporters to facilitate the filing of SARs. Earlier thematic work by the FCA identified instances where a lack of resources in smaller firms had led to backlogs in alerts generated and potential exposure to undisclosed suspicious activity or sanctions breaches. Remedial action, including interventions, was taken.

Reflecting the high volume of reporting and the wide variety of sectors and businesses incorporated into the UK’s AML/CTF regime, there are concerns about the quality of reporting by all reporting entities, including banks. During the on-site visit, some firms indicated that they were sometimes filing SARs in response to unexplained/unusual transactions without additional analysis or investigation. LEAs reported concerns about the quality of the SARs, including that they lacked information on a genuine suspicion of ML/TF.

SARs reporting by banks from Oct 2016 to Sept 2017 were 360,393.

The UK participates in various multilateral fora to seek and provide cooperation. The UK International Crime Bureau (UKICB) is the National Central Bureau for INTERPOL and handled over 264 000 INTERPOL messages in 2016. The Europol Headquarters hosts 185 officers from across UK law enforcement, including regional police officers. Information is regularly exchanged through the Europol Secure Information Exchange Network Application (SIENA) (in 2016, the UK sent 1 836 disseminations relating to ML and received 2 668). The UK is a member of the Five Eyes ML Working Group, which recently established a project to facilitate member countries’ direct sharing of financial information. The UK also hosts the International Anti-Corruption Coordination Centre (IACCC) which combines

⁹ S Cherniavskiy, M Tsytisidze, “Topical issues of using the possibilities of unscheduled documentary audits and other inspections in criminal proceedings’ *Authorities of the National bank of Ukraine on the imposition of administrative fines: interdepartmental scientific-practical conference* (Kyiv 2016) 124.

resource from the UK, Interpol, the United States, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and Singapore to improve intelligence-sharing on grand corruption and ML. Joint investigation teams (JITs) are also actively used. The UK has nine active JITs relating specifically to ML and has completed¹⁰.

In Ukraine, the MoJ and the PGOU are the central authorities for the receipt, processing and allocation of MLA requests. During the investigation stage, the competent authority for incoming and outgoing MLAs is the PGO, who disseminates the requests to the relevant LEA in accordance with the subject matter of the request. At the stage of the court review, the competent authority is the MoJ for both incoming and outgoing MLA requests.

Ukraine has been proactive in seeking international co-operation through outgoing MLA requests with regards to investigations of domestic ML or other major predicate crimes (inter alia, corruption, economic crime, organised crime, drug trafficking and human trafficking). The authorities indicate that the increase in the number of outgoing MLA requests in 2016 in relation to ML and corruption is the result of the intensification of the pre-trial investigation of criminal proceedings related to ML and requests for additional information on criminally-obtained assets in foreign countries.

Between 2010 and 2016, Ukraine sent 30 MLA requests (most of them in 2016) in relation to asset arrests, but none with a view to requesting the final confiscation of assets 59. Substantial amounts of assets were arrested in foreign countries on the basis of a request from the UAs. However, based on meetings with the authorities, and as also substantiated by open sources, the evaluators have been made aware of cases in which Ukraine had not been effective with regard to outgoing MLA requests, by failing to provide requested countries with sufficient evidence in a timely manner to enable them to render a final confiscation order. In particular, it seems that Ukraine has not yet been able to provide requested countries with a Ukrainian final court decision on confiscation, so as to allow foreign courts to render a final confiscation decision.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the current lack of court decisions on the confiscation of seized assets is connected with the ongoing pre-trial investigations into relevant criminal proceedings, since the investigated crimes are complex, requiring a large amount of investigative and other procedural actions.

The FIU in Ukraine is a member of the Egmont Group and adheres strictly to the Group's Principles for the Exchange of Information. The FIU does not need to enter into bilateral or multilateral agreements to co-operate with its counterparts. Nevertheless, the FIU has entered into a MoU with 73 foreign FIUs to facilitate co-operation. Exchange of information is conducted through the Egmont Secure Web.

¹⁰ FATF (2018), Anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing measures – United Kingdom, Fourth Round Mutual Evaluation Report, FATF, Paris <<http://www.fatf-gafi.org/publications/mutualevaluations/documents/mer-united-kingdom2018.html>> accessed 30 December 2018.

In 2014–2016, the FIU sent 1,547 requests to, and received 1,144 responses from foreign FIUs. 103 letters related to spontaneous dissemination of information were sent to foreign counterparts.

Consequently, an important aspect of the Ukrainian system's operation is the exchange of information. UK – JMLIT provides unique opportunities for international co-operation on cases and enhancing international public/private information sharing. LEAs in other countries may submit cases to JMLIT through the NCA. This is a new feature and has not yet been widely used, but, if used regularly, it provides scope to enhance international co-operation. The UKFIU has initiated a pilot to push appropriate inbound Egmont requests through JMLIT. The UK is also championing public/private partnerships in other countries with the goal of establishing a worldwide network of public/private partnerships which could share information between themselves.

The UK is capable of providing assistance in the context of non-conviction based confiscation and related proceedings, including in circumstances where a perpetrator is unavailable by reason of death, flight, absence, or where the perpetrator is unknown. Instrumentalities, proceeds and laundered property can be identified through a range of available investigative measures which can be exercised on behalf of another state (POCA (External Investigations) Order 2013, ss. 6, 13, 16, 22, 29, 40, 47, 50, 56, 63).

A UK court can also issue an order to freeze or confiscate this property, or property of a corresponding value, where there is an ongoing investigation or proceeding in the requesting state, or where a corresponding foreign order has been issued, provided there is dual criminality (POCA (External Requests and Orders) Order 2005, ss. 143, 144, 147, 161).

UK police forces can coordinate on seizure and confiscation with requesting states through police-to-police arrangements, multilateral organizations, or Joint Investigation Teams (JITs). The UK has mechanisms to manage and dispose of property frozen, seized or confiscated on behalf of a foreign state, including the appointment of management receivers or administrators or enforcement receivers (Criminal Justice (International Co-operation) Act 1990 (Enforcement of Overseas Forfeiture Orders) Order 2005, ss. 12, 22).

We should take into account that the UK is able to share confiscated property with other countries and endeavours to enter into 50:50 sharing arrangements the country to which it has provided assistance. Stolen state assets (e.g. the proceeds of corruption) are returned to the requesting state in full, less reasonable expenses.

In particular, it is important that the UK faces significant ML risks from overseas, in particular from other financial centres (including some of its Overseas Territories and Crown Dependencies), due to its position as a major global financial centre and the world's largest centre for cross-border banking. In particular, the UK is vulnerable and at risk of being used as a destination or transit location for criminal

proceeds. Criminal activity in the UK also generates a significant amount of proceeds although domestic crime levels have continued to decrease over the past 20 years. The main money laundering (ML) risks include high-end ML, cash-based ML, and the laundering of proceeds from fraud and tax offences, drug offending and human trafficking, and organized crime. The UK also faces particular and significant risks from laundering the proceeds of foreign predicate crimes, including transnational organized crime and overseas corruption.

The UK faces severe threats from international terrorism. Terrorist financing activity in the UK is usually low-level, involving small amounts of funds raised by UK based individuals to fund their own travel to join terrorist groups, to send to terrorist associates, or to finance their own terrorist attack plans. The UK also faces threats from Northern Ireland-related terrorism which are rated severe in Northern Ireland and substantial in Great Britain. The nature of the Northern Ireland-related terrorism threat has evolved with paramilitaries and terrorist groups focusing on forms of organized crime which are not all specifically intended to raise funds for terrorism. This experience is extremely important for Ukraine, in view of the fact that our state suffers from identical threats, in particular, in uncontrolled areas by the Government of Ukraine and adjacent areas to these territories, but also outside these territories.

The UK has implemented an AML/CFT system that is effective in many respects. Particularly good results are being achieved in the areas of investigation and prosecution of ML/TF, confiscation, the implementation of targeted financial sanctions related to terrorism and proliferation, protecting the non-profit sector from terrorist abuse, understanding the ML/TF risks facing the country, preventing misuse of legal structures and co-operating domestically and internationally to address them. However, major improvements are needed to strengthen supervision and implementation of preventive measures, and ensure that financial intelligence is fully exploited.

In terms of technical compliance, the legal framework is particularly strong with only two areas in need of significant improvements – measures related to correspondent banking and the UKFIU.

The UK has significantly strengthened its AML/CFT framework since its last evaluation particularly in relation to operational co-ordination among law enforcement agencies, stronger investigative tools, mechanisms to facilitate public/private information sharing, and the creation of an authority to address inconsistencies in the supervision of lawyers and accountants. One important issue which is outstanding from the previous assessment is the need to enhance the resources and capabilities available to the UKFIU. This is especially important on the basis that Ukraine should show progress in the formation of a new national legislator AML/CFT, in particular when adopting the aforementioned basic Law to implement EU Directive 2015/849 2015.

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Антон Чубенко

доктор юридичних наук, професор,
директор Академії фінансового моніторингу,
м. Київ, Україна

ДОСВІД ВЕЛИКОЇ БРИТАНІЇ В ПОБУДОВІ НАЦІОНАЛЬНИХ АНТИЛЕГАЛІЗАЦІЙНОЇ ТА АНТИКОРУПЦІЙНОЇ СИСТЕМ В УКРАЇНІ

Анотація. Велика Британія є однією з найбільш відкритих держав у світі. Рівень економічного розвитку в цій країні ґрунтується на широких і продуктивних відносинах для всіх держав світу. Проте необхідно зазначити, що відкритий статус Великої Британії як глобального фінансового центру призводить до ризику незаконних фінансових потоків.

Боротьба з відмиванням коштів і протидія корупції – загальна тенденція, актуальна для всіх держав світу. Стратегічно важливі документи для здійснення податкової політики наявні також у США.

Фінансові органи України, Великої Британії та США є учасниками системи протидії відмиванню коштів і фінансуванню тероризму як на національному, так і на міжнародному рівнях.

Метою статті є вивчення досвіду Великої Британії для побудови антилегалізаційної та антикорупційної систем в Україні.

У 2015–2016 роках Велика Британія та Україна опублікували свої перші національні оцінки ризиків відмивання коштів і фінансування тероризму, визначивши ті сфери, де потрібно вжити заходів, пов'язаних із виявленням доходів і майна, отриманих злочинним шляхом, що надалі використовуються для боротьби з відмиванням коштів та фінансуванням тероризму.

До законодавства нашої держави додаються положення про боротьбу з відмиванням коштів, що відповідають міжнародним стандартам. Зміни режиму звітності про підозрілі операції та наглядовий режим ведуться як у Великій Британії, так і в Україні.

Велика Британія активно проводить розслідування та кримінальне переслідування відмивання коштів і фінансування тероризму (1 400 судових рішень на рік). Правоохоронні органи Великої Британії мають потужні інструменти для отримання вигідної інформації, зокрема й за допомогою державних та приватних зв'язків, а також ефективно використовують цю інформацію у своїх розслідуваннях.

В Україні створено кілька спеціальних органів, ключове місце серед яких посідає Національне агентство України з пошуку, відстеження та управління активами, отриманими від корупції та інших злочинів. Функції цього Агентства зрозумілі для більшості країн світу, але зовсім нові в системі органів державної влади України. У Великій Британії наявне спеціальне законодавство, зокрема Закон про доходи від злочинів 2002 року.

Україна активно долучається до міжнародного співробітництва шляхом надання запитів про відшкодування збитків у зв'язку з розслідуванням внутрішніх протиправних дій або інших злочинів.

Однак варто зазначити, що поточний брак судових рішень про конфіскацію вилученого майна пов'язаний із проведенням досудового слідства у відповідних кримінальних справах, оскільки розслідувані злочини є складними, що потребує виконання великої кількості слідчих та інших процесуальних дій.

Отже, важливий аспект роботи української системи – обмін інформацією. Велика Британія надає унікальні можливості для міжнародного співробітництва у справах та посиленні міжнародного публічного/приватного обміну інформацією. Важливим є те, що суди у Великій Британії також можуть видати наказ про заморожування або конфіскацію власності.

Велика Британія значно посилила свою систему відмивання коштів/фінансування тероризму, особливо у сфері оперативної координації діяльності правоохоронних органів, посилення інструментів розслідування, механізмів для полегшення публічного та приватного обміну інформацією.

Це особливо важливо з огляду на те, що Україна має продемонструвати прогрес у формуванні нового національного законодавства з протидії відмиванню коштів і фінансуванню тероризму, зокрема, прийнявши базовий закон про імплементацію Директиви ЄС2015/849 2015 року. Законопроект № 9417, ініційований урядом України, зареєстровано у парламенті 19 грудня 2018 року як невідкладний.

Ключові слова: запобігання корупції; боротьба з відмиванням грошей; Національне агентство України з пошуку, відстеження та управління активами, отриманими від корупційних та інших злочинів.